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ABSTRACT

Humans are social creatures and hence crave social interaction more than any other, many claim that Humans, when born, are lot more frail than many other animals therefore nature has set up an "attachment" system inside us so that we may survive. In today's world we are losing our ability to connect with our face to face due to the hectic lifestyle we are forced to endure. However we have adapted to the problem we are facing and hence today we witness the new era of instant messaging and socializing with help of social networking websites. U-Connect are the next step in such endeavors to make us feel more in touch with our friends and family. It's an app which allows human interaction on a whole another level when compared to other social networking applications. It will not only allow for instant messaging but also to voice call as well as video call. It will be the ultimate connection app, which will be connecting people across the globe and bind them with all form of technical communication. We wish to provide users with the experience of smooth and easy to operate application with all the tools for instant communication that mankind has developed. This app will be the bridge of connection among it's users hence has the fitting name U-Connect.

KEYWORDS: U-connect, Viber, whatsapp, skype, video, text.

INTRODUCTION

U-Connect are web based app made for various platforms like Android, Windows, Ios, and many more. The multiplatform feature ensures that you stay connected no matter the type of operating system used. It also makes the app versatile and easy to use as you may switch your phone and operating system freely and without any need to re-register.

It features all forms of technical communication which are instant messaging, voice calling, and video calling. All these ensure that any need of communication can be sated without any complications, as well as makes sure that you can easily manage your communications in an orderly fashions as all chats and calls are available at the same place.

In simpler words U-Connect is an app that allows you to send text messages, images videos, and documents as well as allows you to video call and voice call making sure to fulfill every communication needs one might have.

The app is very versatile in nature easy to use and contains no advertisements. Advertisements are easily a turnoff that throws a number of clients to the winds and decreases the interest one has in the application.

The app also uses end to end encryption hence provides good security to the application making your chats and calls secure.

This type of encryption that uses Public Key encryption which is a technique that uses two keys both for sending and receiving end.

This type of encryption ensures that the key need not be transferred and hence can't be stolen during the process of data transfer.

PREVIOUS PROBLEMS

There are a number of apps which provide us with a number of options for social communication. The leading ones in their own segments are –

Whatsapp- Instant Text Messaging.

Viber - Voice Calling.

Skype – Video Calling.

However managing three accounts in three different apps can be a bit of a handful as well as keeping track of all conversations we had with different people on different apps.

These apps may be the leaders in their chosen segments but they still have their weak points such as-

Whatsapp:-

- It saves the files by default, so great privacy threat.
- You can just send 100 messages in a month to friends not having Whatsapp on their phone.
- The size of the data bundle that can be uploaded is very small.

Viber:-

- Security is not impressive and easily broken in.
- Everyone should install and register to use Viber again, if you change your number.

Skype:-

- International calls still cost money.
- Still some technical issues with the app.

These dilemmas lead to the concept of the app U-Connect.

METHADODOLOGY

Upon installation of the app the user would be credited an account for the phone number currently employed in the device.

U-Connect will use a customized version of the open standard Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP). Seeing the advantages of XMPP it makes an ideal choice for instant messaging. Multimedia messages will be sent by uploading the image, audio or video to be sent to an HTTP server and then sending a link to the content along with its Base64 encoded thumbnail. The user would not even have to add them manually as the app automatically compares all the phone numbers from the device's address book with its central database of U-connect users to automatically add contacts to the user's U-Connect contact list.

The app will follow a 'store and forward' mechanism for exchanging messages between two users. When a user sends a message, it first travels to the U-connect's server where it is stored. Then the server repeatedly requests the receiver acknowledge receipt of the message. As soon as the message is acknowledged, the server drops the message; it is no longer available in the database of the server. U-connect server keeps the message only for 30 days in its database when it is not delivered.

This mechanism not only allows the message to be delivered without fail but also keeps the message intact for the next 30 days just in case the user does not acknowledge the receipt of the message.

With U-Connect the communications will be to provide additional security end-to-end encrypted to provide additional security. Users will also be able to verify contacts' identities, since they will be registered on the app's main database.

CONCLUSION

The app has great market potential as well as holds great promise. It not only provides us with all forms of communication on a single platform but also has the capability to capture market of three different segments which are- instant messaging, voice calling, and video calling.

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